

LoRa-Augmented Static Positioning System (LSPS)

Motivation: Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS)[1], including GPS, determine position by trilateration of satellite pseudoranges derived from precisely time-stamped signals; accuracy is governed by receiver clock stability, satellite geometry (position dilution of precision, PDOP), and propagation through the ionosphere and troposphere. To reach centimeter-level accuracy[2], receivers (or offboard software such as RTKLIB) can run carrier-phase modes—real-time kinematic (RTK)[3,4], which uses low-latency base-station or network corrections, or precise point positioning (PPP)[5–9], which relies on precise orbit/clock products after a convergence period. In edge deployments typical of agriculture and field robotics, performance degrades due to multipath and blockage from canopy [10–12], structures[13], and machinery; as well as time-varying atmospheric delay; receiver drift and long time-to-first-fix. Additionally, periods of poor satellite geometry that inflate PDOP, even with adequate signal strength.

Practical constraints also compound issues for navigation: dual-frequency/RTK operation draws on the order of 100–300 mW power[14], correction links require reliable backhaul, under-canopy or metallic environments cause frequent loss of lock [15,16], and dual-frequency hardware plus base-station siting add cost and complexity to the system. Thus, while *GNSS excels in open sky, it is brittle for low-power, under-canopy, or intermittently connected systems*—motivating a complementary, locally managed positioning layer that remains available when GNSS falters.

Why LoRa? LoRa (Long Range)[17] is a compelling substrate for local positioning in field environments because it provides long-range communication at very low power in foliage-tolerant sub-GHz bands, enabling *robust operation under canopy*[18].

By emitting deterministic beacons from static anchors with coordinates presurveyed by precision GPS units, a LoRa mesh network can establish a *stable local reference frame* that remains available even when the sky is obscured and GNSS is unreliable.

Not only can LoRa leverage the same radio infrastructure commonly deployed for *telemetry* and *command*, which can be *repurposed to form a positioning grid*, but it also supports an *edge-first architecture*[19] in which the operator controls the physical and medium-access layers and the network topology, avoiding dependence on wide-area backhaul, thereby improving efficiency and reducing system complexity[20].

One key limitation of LoRa is its accuracy: *LoRa-only ranging generally cannot achieve the centimeter-level performance*[20] of RTK-enabled GNSS; but instead **meter-scale estimates are typical**. However, *when combined with complementary sensors—such as wheel odometry*[21,22], *inertial measurements, and visual cues—LoRa-based positioning can deliver practical sub-meter performance* in a wide range of agricultural robotics applications.

Solution: We developed a two-tier LoRa positioning architecture optimized for under-canopy operation. **Tier 1** would employ a two-way time-of-flight (double-sided ranging)[23] on sub-GHz SX126x radios to obtain meter-scale ranges to three or more static anchors per cell; these measurements are solved by least-squares lateration and fused with wheel odometry and IMU readings in an extended Kalman filter [23] to

provide continuous, drift-bounded pose. **Tier 2** is augmented coverage with short-range SX1280 **micro-anchors**, selectively deployed in **high-value zones** (e.g., block boundaries and alleys in the target field) to increase the update rate and tighten local accuracy to the sub-meter regime during critical maneuvers. The system can utilize the raw LoRa PHY [24] for precise timestamping, applies per-device delay calibration, and duty-cycles ranging to minimize power and airtime, while opportunistically ingesting GNSS data where available, to maintain global frame consistency without relying on it for continuity.

Physical Layout LSPS deploys static LoRa anchors at pre-surveyed coordinates to create overlapping coverage cells that ensure each rover can “hear” at least three anchors at any location within the designated spatial coordinates. Anchors are mounted 1.5–2.5 m above ground on posts to improve Fresnel clearance and reduce ground reflections, spaced roughly 60–120 m in open fields and 30–60 m for operation under dense canopy. Consistent antenna type, orientation, and gain are maintained across the network to stabilize link budgets and simplify calibration; cell boundaries are conceptualized as Voronoi regions to guide placement and density decisions.

To evaluate the behavior of the physical layout, we built a 2-D Monte Carlo simulator that places anchors on grids of variously scaled lattice sizes according to a pre-defined field dimension. For any given lattice, the **structure was tested by randomly introducing perturbations and randomized rover positions over the field polygon** using a log-distance path-loss with log-normal shadowing ($n \approx 2.2\text{--}3.2$ open; $3.0\text{--}4.0$ canopy; $\sigma = 4\text{--}10$ dB). To estimate the per-link SNR, height/Fresnel terms were added.

Figure 1. Dense canopy simulation results. **A Condition-number map:** Values hover around 1.2–1.8 across the field, which indicates well-conditioned geometry for lateration almost everywhere in the selected grid **B Coverage heatmap:** Most cells hear 6 anchors; a few edge/corner cells drop to 5 or 4, but overall $p(\geq 3) = 1.00$, indicating that the coverage is robust even under dense-canopy assumptions

After this parametrization, we calculated (i) the probability of a given rover hearing ≥ 3 anchors, (ii) the average number of anchors heard, and (iii) a 2-D geometry metric (e.g., condition number of the range Jacobian). The simulation was initialized for a

parameter sweep to test (a) **anchor spacing** between 30 to 150 m, (b) **beacon placement height** 1 to 3 m, and (c) **canopy attenuation** between +0 to 12 dB to produce coverage/geometry heatmaps and derive recommended densities. Additionally, to simulate dense-canopy conditions, the following parameterization is initialized: propagation is modeled with a log-distance path-loss exponent $n=3.8$, log-normal shadowing $\sigma=6$ dB, an added canopy attenuation of 12 dB per link, and an 8 dB Fresnel clearance penalty when the first Fresnel zone intrudes at the midpoint. Radios would operate at 915 MHz with 125 kHz bandwidth and SF10 (demodulation threshold -15

dB), transmit power 14 dBm, 2 dBi TX/RX antennas, and a 6 dB receiver noise figure; the noise floor is $-174+10\log_{10}BW+NF$ dBm. The field is 300 m \times 180 m with rover samples placed at every 10 m; anchors are at 2.0 m height, and the rover antenna at 0.5 m; no lattice jitter or rotation was included in the sweep. Optimizing for the coarsest lattice subject to $p(\geq 3 \text{ anchors heard}) \geq 0.95$ and mean lateration-Jacobian condition number ≤ 3.0 selected spacings $s_x = 150$ m and $s_y = 110$ m (**six anchors total**), yielding $p(\geq 3) = 1.00$, an average of 5.77 anchors heard per point, and a mean condition number of 1.49.

The simulation results indicated that the coverage would be robust even under dense canopy conditions, with 100% of the 400 rover placement positions hearing ≥ 3 anchors and well-conditioned geometry for lateration almost everywhere in the selected grid (*Figure 1*).

Field Deployment Tests: We deployed a pair of Semtech SX1280 radios at the University of Illinois Energy Farm to quantify latency (via inter-packet intervals) and link reliability under a nominal 5 s transmit schedule. Over the analyzed window (18 Sep 2025 10:53 to 23 Sep 2025 08:11; 4.89 days), **84,454** packets were received. The inter-packet distribution was tightly centered at 5 s (mean = 5.001 s, median = 5.000 s), with rare jitter (4–6 s) and only **two** episodes of loss, each expressed as a 10 s interval with a single missing sequence number. Modeling the occurrence of these loss episodes as a homogeneous Poisson process yields an estimated rate of $\lambda = 0.409$ day (95% CI: 0.050–1.478), equivalent to 0.017 h^{-1} ; on a per-packet basis this corresponds to approximately 2.4×10^{-5} episodes per packet. With only two events observed, no diurnal pattern can be inferred from this dataset.

Swarm-Based Navigation Algorithm Development & Testing

Swarm robotics and distributed sensing in Agriculture

Recent advances in swarm robotics suggest that multiple small autonomous robots can collaboratively monitor crops and soil more efficiently than a single large machine. For example, replacing a single 270 kW tractor with a swarm of ten 24 kW robotic tractors has been shown to greatly reduce fuel consumption, soil compaction, and costs while maintaining the same field capacity[25–27]. Swarms of drones or ground robots can cover large fields in parallel, sharing data to pinpoint areas of stress or infection. Inspired by social insects, autonomous farm drones using swarm intelligence algorithms (e.g. ant colony or bee foraging strategies) have been demonstrated to collectively monitor crop conditions – they efficiently survey vast areas, detect issues like pest hotspots or dry zones, and adapt to changing field conditions without centralized control[28]. This decentralized approach yields robust coverage and timely data for agricultural management.

In tandem with robotics, distributed sensor networks (IoT nodes) are being deployed across farmlands to create an integrated picture of soil and plant health. A 2022 survey highlighted that wireless sensor networks (WSNs) combined with machine learning are now applied in many smart farming scenarios [29–31]. Networks of low-cost sensors can continuously measure soil moisture, temperature, nutrient levels, or even specific pathogen biomarkers. These static sensors augment mobile robots: while robots provide mobility and targeted sensing (such as imaging or volatile sampling at various locations), in-ground or stationary sensors provide continuous local monitoring. Together, swarms of robots and distributed sensors form a collaborative sensing web that can detect early signs of soil-borne disease or plant stress across large fields in real time. For instance, multiple ground robots equipped with cameras and volatile organic compound (VOC) detectors can scout different rows simultaneously, while an overhead drone swarm maps canopy temperature and color changes – this multi-agent, multi-modal sensing dramatically increases spatio-temporal coverage of crop conditions[32–34]. Such distributed systems improve precision agriculture by enabling “plant-level” monitoring at farm scale. Key research challenges remain in coordinating these swarms (communication, navigation, and energy management) and in data fusion from many sensors, but recent testbeds are promising. European field trials (e.g. the SAGA project) have already deployed UAV swarms to collectively monitor weeds and crop health in sugar beet fields, demonstrating the feasibility of multi-robot sensing for pest management. Swarm robotics thus provides a scalable platform for disease surveillance in agriculture, offering redundancy (if one unit fails, others fill in) and minimal human labor for continuous monitoring.[29,30]

For our project, we are implementing decentralized swarm coordination protocols [35–38] designed to achieve reliable and efficient coverage across agricultural plots. Initial development is carried out in simulation, using a 20×20 grid abstraction of an approximately 1-acre field, where each grid cell corresponds to a $5' \times 5'$ spatial resolution target.

Early tests of deterministic quadrant-based approaches demonstrated limitations, particularly under time constraints, where rigid pathing led to inefficiencies and uneven coverage (*Figure 5*). To address these challenges, we developed a hybrid coordination strategy that combines **pheromone-trail-based stigmergy** [39,40] with **repulsion behaviors** [41] inspired by *boid models* [42,43], supplemented by *spiral fallback trajectories* [44] to resolve deadlocks and fill residual coverage gaps. In this design,

Figure 2. Examples of coverage achieved from various pathing and swarm behavior simulations to test algorithms. Simulations were parameterized targeting 15-minute intervals per visit per cell, and 3x minimum coverage per cell per 45 min patrol duration. A. Random walk with center start B. Quadrant assignment, serpentine pathing, C. Quadrant assignment, Spiral pathing, D. Spiral fallback pathing with pheromone trail that disappears in 15 minutes, with random walk and repulsion to pick next destination.

rovers deposit virtual pheromone markers within a *shared lattice map* broadcast over the LoRa mesh network, which biases subsequent rover movement decisions toward under-sampled areas, while pairwise repulsion prevents clustering and redundant sampling. Spiral fallback trajectories ensure local coverage completion when pheromone gradients become ambiguous.

Simulation results show that this hybrid approach achieved $>3x$ average cell coverage within a 45-minute patrol window using 100 rovers, demonstrating both efficiency and resilience to variable deployment conditions. Equivalent coverage performance was achieved with only 10 rovers when the lattice was scaled back to $1' \times 2'$ cells ($\sim 1/3$ -acre field). We will perform sand-box trials with prototype rovers (*Figure 2*) to test for power budget and mobility under algorithmic navigation constraints to further

confirm operational parameters and scalability. These results will reveal the limits of the proposed system for adaptability from small-scale controlled experiments to larger field environments while maintaining spatial resolution requirements by scaling the number of rovers in the fleet- which will directly translate to operational cost.

Actuation for Data Collection, Transmission, and Storage Logic

We will implement an actuated sensing architecture that integrates multimodal cameras and spectroscopic probes mounted on a mobile rover. Each sensor $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbf{S}$ acquires data streams $\mathbf{d}_s(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{t})$ where (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) denote geospatial coordinates and \mathbf{t} the temporal index. The sensor set is defined as $\mathbf{S} = \{\mathbf{C}\uparrow, \mathbf{C}\downarrow, \mathbf{Cz}, \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{S}\}$ with $\mathbf{C}\uparrow$ the upward-facing canopy camera, $\mathbf{C}\downarrow$ the downward-facing ground camera, \mathbf{Cz} the zoom-capable camera on a robotic arm, \mathbf{R} the Raman/SERS probe, and \mathbf{S} the broadband spectrophotometer.

Actuation for Data Collection Model

Each sensor \mathbf{s} is associated with an actuation state $a_s(\mathbf{t}) \in \{0, 1\}$, where $a_s(\mathbf{t})=1$ indicates active acquisition. Actuation is governed by a control policy $a_s(\mathbf{t}) = f_s(\phi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{t}), \theta_s)$ where $\phi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{t})$ represents environmental triggers (e.g., anomaly scores, revisit requests) and θ_s are sensor-specific thresholds (e.g., detection confidence, illumination). The robotic arm defines a kinematic map $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{t}))$ where $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{t}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are joint angles and $\mathbf{T}(\cdot)$ is the forward kinematics yielding probe position $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{t}) \in \mathbb{R}^3$. This ensures precise alignment of visual, Raman and spectrophotometer probes with tissue targets.

Figure 3. *Leo Rover is a small-sized, four-wheeled, open-source robotic platform manufactured and developed in Wrocław, Poland, by fictionlab [45,46]. It weighs approximately 7 kgs and can carry a payload of 5 kgs with dimensions (LxWxH) 424 mm x 445 mm x 303 mm*

This ensures precise alignment of visual, Raman and spectrophotometer probes with tissue targets.

Data Transmission and Storage Logic

Data packets are defined as $P_s(\mathbf{t}) = \{d_s(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{t}), m_s(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{t})\}$, where d_s is the raw observation and m_s associated metadata (GNSS/LoRa timestamp, pose). A priority weight $\pi_s \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is assigned to each modality, establishing a storage–transmission hierarchy as $\pi_{\mathbf{R}}, \pi_{\mathbf{S}} \gg \pi_{\mathbf{Cz}} > \pi_{\mathbf{C}\downarrow} > \pi_{\mathbf{C}\uparrow}$.

The transmission scheduler minimizes bandwidth cost subject to priority constraints:

$$\min \sum_{s \in \mathbf{S}} \pi_s E[L_s(\mathbf{t})],$$

Where $L_s(\mathbf{t})$ is the latency for transmitting package $P_s(\mathbf{t})$. High-priority packets (\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{S}) are transmitted immediately ($L_s(\mathbf{t}) \approx 0$), medium-priority packets ($\mathbf{C}\downarrow, \mathbf{Cz}$) are compressed and queued, while low-priority streams ($\mathbf{C}\uparrow$) are downsampled to summary statistics.

System Integration

The *aggregate data set* feeds directly into the **geospatial tensor representation** for AI models– to build an integrated actuation+data pipeline, and can be expressed as

$$D(\mathbf{t}) = \bigcup_{s \in \mathbf{S}} a_s(\mathbf{t}) \cdot P_s(\mathbf{t}),$$

Each active sensor contributes a measurement denoted $d_s(x,y,t)$ where s is an element of the set of sensor identifiers S , (x,y) are orthorectified geospatial coordinates, and t is the GNSS/LoRa synchronized timestamp. For every d_s , a metadata packet $m_s(x,y,t)$ that consists of *pose data*- defining rover position, orientation, arm joint angles, *timestamp* that is generated through GNSS + LoRa synchronization, *calibration metrics*- such as white/gray panel references, laser power settings, and spectrometer gain, and other *quality flags* such as SNR, motion blur, and outlier rejection thresholds. $D(t)$ is stored locally on solid-state drives and partially transmitted via LoRa in real time. In short, *the integrated data stream is not just "sensor data," but a rich, time-stamped, geolocated composite of raw measurements + metadata + contextual covariates + treatment factors + priority tags*. This logic guarantees that multimodal sensing operates adaptively, balancing actuation effort, bandwidth, and scientific value, and is fed directly into an AI-ready tensor data structure ($X(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H \times W}$).

Multi-modal Data Integration & Geospatial Alignment

We propose an integrated framework that will combine the strengths of deep learning for spatiotemporal feature extraction with classical geospatial correlation correction [47–49] to improve the robustness of the data collection and integration. To enable holistic inference across heterogeneous sensing modalities, we will *rasterize all measurements into a common geospatial tensor representation* [50,51].

All imagery and spectral measurements will be orthorectified into the **State Plane Coordinate System, Illinois East Zone (NAD83, EPSG:3435)**, ensuring a consistent (x,y) reference frame for all rasterized data products. For this model, we will let Π_{IL-E} denote the projection operator for the Illinois East State Plane zone (eg, NAD83). Then any geodetic coordinate (ϕ, λ, h) will be mapped to the projected system by

$$(x,y) = \Pi_{IL-E}(\phi, \lambda, h)$$

where (x,y) are the orthorectified map coordinates in meters.

Each modality—RGB imagery, thermal maps, hyperspectral indices, Raman/SERS biomarkers, and broadband reflectance spectra—will be orthorectified and aligned to a fixed spatial grid (GeoTIFF format), indexed by geographic coordinates (x,y) and temporal index t . The resulting dataset will be represented as a four-dimensional tensor $X \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times C \times H \times W}$ where T denotes the number of temporal slices, C the concatenated modality channels, and (H, W) the spatial dimensions. This representation permits analysis with **3D convolutional neural networks (CNNs)** that learn filters $K \in \mathbb{R}^{t \times k \times k}$ operating simultaneously across time and space, producing feature maps with nonlinearity $\sigma(\cdot)$ as

$$F_{t,i,j} = \sigma \left(\sum_{\Delta t_1, \Delta x, \Delta y} K_{\Delta t_1, \Delta x, \Delta y} \cdot X_{t+\Delta t, c, i+\Delta x, j+\Delta y} \right)$$

Generative adversarial networks (GANs) will further be employed to impute missing modalities or forecast patch evolution, optimizing an objective function, represented as

$$\min_G \max_D E[\log D(X)] + E_{\hat{X}}[\log(1 - D(G(\hat{X})))] + \lambda \|G(\hat{X}) - X\|_1,$$

where \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{D} denote two models in competition: *generator* and *discriminator*, respectively, and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is the corrupted or partial input. While \mathbf{G} learns to map input noise or conditional features to synthetic output, \mathbf{D} learns to distinguish between real samples \mathbf{X} and generated ones $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$. The training objective function consists of a minmax optimization, with a composite loss function that will consist of semivariogram loss \mathcal{L}_γ , reconstruction loss \mathcal{L}_{rec} of the CNN, and temporal consistency loss \mathcal{L}_{tmp} combined to create full generator loss in an additive manner, starting with the adversarial loss \mathcal{L}_{adv}

$$\mathcal{L}_G = \mathcal{L}_{\text{adv}} + \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}} + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_\gamma + \lambda_3 \mathcal{L}_{\text{tmp}}$$

Spatial autocorrelation inherent in repeated measurements and local substrate effects will be corrected using *semivariogram models*. The empirical semivariance is defined as

$\gamma(\mathbf{h}) = \frac{1}{2N(\mathbf{h})} \sum_{(i,j) \in N(\mathbf{h})} (Z(\mathbf{x}_i) - Z(\mathbf{x}_j))^2$ where $N(\mathbf{h})$ is the set of location pairs separated by lag distance \mathbf{h} , and $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbf{x})$ is the observed value at location \mathbf{x} . Fitted models (e.g., spherical or exponential) will be used both to decorrelate features prior to learning and to weight kriging-based interpolations. *Disease patch maps* will be generated through geospatial interpolation of measurement intensities, defining probability fields $P_{\text{disease}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = \mathbb{P}(\mathbf{Z}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) \geq \theta \mid \mathbf{X})$ with threshold θ informed by pre-testing calibration baseline. Polygonal disease patches will then be delineated by thresholding and morphological filtering of P_{disease} and stored with associated uncertainty metrics derived from kriging variance.

Intervention Once disease patch polygons are delineated, they will be operationalized into actionable prescriptions for targeted interventions (**Figure 4**). Each polygon will be exported as a geospatial vector layer (GeoJSON or shapefile) containing centroid coordinates, boundary vertices, and associated uncertainty scores. These layers will be ingested into a tasking engine that generates waypoints for an autonomous aerial spraying platform. Specifically, the *polygon boundaries will be discretized into rasterized spray zones*, and flight trajectories will be computed to ensure full coverage with minimal overlap, subject to buffer zones that prevent drift into unaffected areas. The drone's onboard navigation will receive these trajectories in the same State Plane coordinate system (EPSG:3435), ensuring direct compatibility with rover-generated maps.

Spray volume and duration will be parameterized by disease probability intensity, $P_{\text{disease}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)$, allowing dose modulation proportional to the estimated severity field, where $D(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)$ denotes the prescribed dosage at spatial coordinate (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) and time t , while α, β are weighting coefficients tuned during calibration.

In this manner (**Figure 4**), **the disease patch maps not only function as diagnostic layers but also serve as dynamic control inputs for precision actuation, linking sensing, modeling, and intervention in a closed-loop framework.**

$$D(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = \alpha P_{\text{disease}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) + \beta \sigma_K^2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t)$$

Figure 4. Conceptual data-to-actuation process for SentinelCPS **A.** Anchor positioning & field polygon generation **B.** Processing the data to flag hazard zones **C.** Hazard severity estimation, and **D.** Treatment rate prescription

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